

East Boston's Community Commons

Visions Survey

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Conducted by Community Commons

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INTRODUCTION

Community Commons, a group of active residents from across the neighborhood, believe that effective community development requires the meaningful involvement of the residents in the decision-making process. We have the right to shape community development to meet our needs and vision. To that end, this survey, the second in a series on development issues in East Boston, is focused on understanding the current residents' vision of the neighborhood's future.

Community Commons worked with a team of graduate students from Northeastern University to develop a series of surveys to answer these questions. Once the surveys were developed, Dr. Neenah Estrella-Luna, a professor at Northeastern and an East Boston resident, served as the principle investigator to assist Community Commons in developing and implementing this survey. From September 2013 through January 2014, residents from across the neighborhood distributed surveys on paper and online in English and Spanish to their neighbors, at neighborhood association meetings, at community events, and via online networks. In the end, 395 surveys from East Boston residents were collected (margin of error $\pm 5\%$). Dr. Estrella-Luna oversaw the process to ensure that the survey was administered properly and that data was entered accurately. She analyzed the data under the direction of Community Commons members.

Overall, amenities and services that support daily quality of life, like dog parks and high quality open space, were highly desired by residents. Services to support greater social and economic mobility, like English language classes, better public transportation, and office space, were also desired. Residents are also seeking developments that provide entertainment, particularly family oriented entertainment, and live performance venues. Finally, a clear majority were also seeking more opportunities to participate in discussions of issues that affect East Boston residents.

SUMMARY OF RESULTS

Who filled out the survey?

The respondents to the survey are a cross-section of the neighborhood. Consistent with the previous Community Commons survey, slightly more than half of participants are female and the majority are US born and working age-adults. Consistent with the neighborhood demographics, the majority of participants were either non-Hispanic White or Latino. A special effort was made in this survey to ensure robust participation of the Latino community, which comprised 40% of respondents. As a consequence, there is slight over-representation of the Maverick Square section of the neighborhood. This notwithstanding, the distribution of participation is consistent with distribution of the population across the different sections of the neighborhood. In short, the majority of participants were from the Eagle Hill, Orient Heights, and Jeffries Point sections, which is where most East Boston residents live. Consistent with the previous survey, the overwhelming majority of participants are registered to vote.

Source: MrJARichards. (2014). Retrieved from http://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:East_boston_neighborhood_map_ol.svg

A Vision for East Boston: A place to live

A majority of participating residents stated that they wanted more amenities that support our daily quality of life.

Participants stated that East Boston is in need of more parking, places for active recreation, parks, dog parks, and access to affordable fresh foods. The desire for access to fresh food, parking, and parks was consistent across geography and different demographic groups.

However, the need for other amenities varied greatly. White, college educated, and English speaking residents were significantly more likely than others to want more dog parks.

Residents in Eagle Hill and Maverick Square, Latino residents, and those with a high school education or less were more likely than other groups to want more active recreation.

Overall, most participating residents did not see the need for additional handicapped parking.

In written comments, litter and cleanliness was a common complaint among all participating residents across the neighborhood. Solutions offered included additional trash pickup, more public bins, and increased enforcement of sanitation laws.

A Vision for East Boston: A place for opportunity

East Boston residents would like to have more services that would support the opportunity to be socially and economically mobile. A majority of residents also would like to see more and better public transit. The need for better bike-related infrastructure and access was the most common statement in written comments.

“Better connections to downtown via bicycling. Current Blue line regulations make it hard to commute via bicycle. Maybe a bike car on the Blue line? A footbridge to downtown would be amazing.”

- Day Square/ Wood Island resident

A majority of residents see the need for opportunities to learn to speak English. However, the perceived need for this particular service varied considerably. Foreign born, non-English speaking residents, those with a high school education or less, and Latino residents overwhelmingly reported the need for more English Language classes.

This difference in perceived needs for services that create opportunity is also seen in the desire for daycare. The perceived need for daycare varied by education, ethnicity, and income. Households with two or more children are much more likely to want more daycare than households with only one child. Interestingly, households with zero children are also more likely to see the need for more daycare.

The need for childcare extends beyond access to a safe place for children while parents are at work. In written comments, one parent described the difficulty of maintaining healthy habits without access to child care.

“As a single parent living in Eastie, it’s hard to find a way to be active and have a babysitter. The Y’s babysitting is limited.”

- Eagle Hill resident

A Vision for East Boston: Thoughtful commercial development

Overall, East Boston residents would like to see more locally oriented and low impact development. Office space and retail were seen as needed across the neighborhood. However the desire for this varies across different demographic groups. Whites were more likely to want less office development while Latinos were more likely to want more office development.

Community Commons Survey - Vision

The desire for industrial development is split across the neighborhood. Industrial development varies primarily by ethnicity, education, income, and section of the neighborhood. White, college educated, higher income residents, as well as those living in Jeffries Point and Orient Heights strongly prefer less industrial development. Non-white, non-college educated, lower income residents, as well as Maverick and Central Square residents, desire more industrial development.

The desire for more industrial development was not associated with desire for more jobs. Several residents across the neighborhood wrote comments about the need for more job opportunities, job training, and learning how to start a business. These residents were generally in favor of office development over industrial development.

"I'd also love to see more discussion about creating good jobs for blue-collar workers and working class families."

- Day Square/ Wood Island resident

"More opportunities for new and small businesses; how to start a business in the US."

- Central Square resident

A Vision for East Boston: Entertainment for East Boston residents

There is a strong desire for entertainment venues in East Boston. Unsurprisingly, the type of entertainment desired varies across demographic groups. A plurality of residents would like the development of nightlife venues. However, this desire is primarily found among the White, college educated, middle and higher income residents of the neighborhood. The most common form of nightlife found in the written comments were restaurants, bars, and places to go dancing.

A majority of residents would also like more live performance venues. This desire was strongest among those with a high school education or less, lower income, and female residents.

While many of the written comments expressed the desire for age appropriate and adult oriented entertainment, the vast majority of residents stated that East Boston needs more places for family entertainment like movie theaters. The desire for more family oriented entertainment options was strongest among residents living in Maverick Square and Orient Heights.

"Why not build a complex for families to spend time together as Revere Beach used to be?"

- Orient Heights resident

A Vision for East Boston: Housing for all

A significant majority of residents want both more affordable housing and more market rate housing.

There is variation in who prefers what type of housing. Higher income residents are the most likely to desire more market rate housing and less affordable housing. Lower income residents and those with a high school education or less strongly desire more affordable housing. Women, non-whites, and Maverick Square residents also expressed the need for more affordable housing.

A very small number of participants wrote comments explicitly stating the desire for gentrification. These residents were overwhelmingly native born, college educated, English speaking residents in Eagle Hill and Jeffries Point. However, the majority of participating residents expressed the need for a diversity of housing types from "luxury" to affordable.

"More affordable homes (I am not only referring to housing [projects]) to avoid gentrification."

- Jeffries Point resident

"Encourage market rate housing throughout East Boston."

- Orient Heights resident

A Vision for East Boston: A diverse neighborhood

Overall, a significant majority of residents are either happy with the level and type of diversity in East Boston or want more diversity. One interesting pattern found was that those who want more market rate housing also expressed the desire for less diversity in the neighborhood. In general, White, college educated, and higher income residents are satisfied with the amount or type of diversity in the neighborhood. Non-white (including Latino), lower income, and non-college educated residents would like to see more diversity. Males, those with a Bachelor’s degree, and those with moderate to high incomes were more likely to desire less diversity in the neighborhood.

One of the strongest predictors for the preference for diversity was the reason for moving to or living in East Boston. Those who moved to or live in East Boston because of friends and family want more diversity. Those who were born and raised in East Boston or who moved here because of their job were more likely to desire less diversity.

In the written comments, diversity was discussed primarily as a desire for more variety in restaurants to reflect the many cultures living in the neighborhood as well as the many tastes amongst the residents.

However, there was a very small group of participants who objected to the presence of undocumented immigrants. Participants making these comments were primarily male, English speaking, native born residents who were born and raised in East Boston.

A Vision for East Boston: A place with engaged residents

A majority of residents desire more opportunities to discuss local issues. Written comments reveal that participating residents were interested in community building and increasing opportunities for cross-cultural learning.

“I would love to see more activities that bring together the diverse communities of East Boston.”
 - Jeffries Point resident

“Less politics, more community.”
 - Eagle Hill resident

The desire for increased opportunity for public discourse varied. There were significant differences in opportunities to be civically engaged by race, education, and neighborhood section. In general, White and residents with a college education are happy with the opportunities to discuss local issues. Latino residents and those with a high school education or less are more likely to want more opportunities to discuss local issues.

Residents of Central Square, Day Square/Wood Island, and Maverick Square are less likely to be happy with opportunities to discuss local issues. In contrast, residents of Eagle Hill, Jeffries Point, and Orient Heights are more likely to be satisfied with opportunities to discuss local issues. It should be noted that these three sections of the neighborhood have longstanding neighborhood associations, which could explain the difference in experience. There were several written comments expressing the desire for more interaction across East Boston.

“More interaction between neighborhood groups.”
 - Maverick Square resident

CONCLUSION

The vision of a future East Boston is one where people will choose to live here, that continues the long tradition of being a place of opportunity, where future development provides assets to the residents of East Boston, with housing to accommodate a variety of incomes. Along with this, residents expressed the desire for more opportunities for civic engagement and public dialogue.

The variation in the perceived need for certain services or amenities points to the need to promote greater interaction across the diversity of residents. These results highlight many areas of commonality but also reveal important differences that are strongly related to race and class, as well as the reason for living in or moving to the neighborhood. One area of consensus, however, was the deep love of this community. A large number of participants stated that they moved into East Boston for a variety of reasons but choose to stay here because of the community.

This study raises as many questions as it answers. What we cannot determine from this survey is what kind of industrial development would be acceptable or unacceptable to those who desire more of it. The results also raise the question about how East Boston residents define “affordable housing.” Finally, it is not clear what diversity means across the diversity of participating residents. Future studies should explore those issues to better understand how to bridge some of the differences identified in this survey.

East Boston would benefit from tapping into the expressed desire for more opportunities to discuss local issues by engaging all residents in deliberative discussions about the future development in the neighborhood. A future that meets the needs of current and future residents requires a different approach to community and economic development than has been historically done. East Boston residents are ready for that.

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APPENDIX A: DESCRIPTION OF THE SURVEY RESPONDENTS

<u>Gender</u>				<u>Race/ Ethnicity</u>			
		#	%		#	%	
	Female	210	55%		White	196	49%
	Male	172	45%		Latino/ Hispanic	167	42%
	Androgynous	1	<1%		Black/ African American	11	3%
					Mixed	10	3%
					Asian	5	1%
<u>Age</u>					American Indian/ Alaskan Native	4	1%
	12-18	15	4%		Arab	1	<1%
	19-24	33	9%		Brazilian	1	<1%
	25-44	204	53%		Cape Verdean	1	<1%
	45-64	113	30%		Native Hawaiian/ Pacific Islander	1	<1%
	65-74	15	4%				
	75 or greater	3	1%				
<u>Nativity</u>				<u>Education</u>			
	US Born	241	65%		Less than High School ¹	58	15%
	Foreign Born ¹	131	35%		High school/ GED	85	23%
					Some College	40	11%
<u>Children in the household</u>					Vocational/ Technical/ Associates	19	5%
	0 ¹	232	59%		Bachelor's degree ²	108	29%
	1	79	20%		Graduate degree or higher ²	65	17%
	2 or more	81	21%				
				<u>Individual Income</u>			
<u>Voter Registration Status</u>					Less than \$10,000 ¹	36	12%
	Registered to vote	278	75%		\$10,000 - 24,999	62	20%
	Not registered to vote	48	13%		\$25,000 - 49,999	97	31%
	Ineligible to vote at this time	44	12%		\$50,000 - 74,999	65	21%
					More than \$75,000 ²	51	16%
<u>Neighborhood of Residence</u>				<u>Primary Language</u>			
	Central Square	26	7%		English	249	64%
	Day Square/ Wood Island	19	5%		Spanish ¹	129	33%
	Eagle Hill	106	30%		Portuguese	5	1%
	Jeffries Point	60	17%		Italian	4	1%
	Maverick Square ³	67	19%		Arabic	1	<1%
	Orient Heights	72	21%		Cape Verdean	1	<1%
	Not sure	29	8%		Vietnamese	1	<1%

¹These residents are underrepresented in the sample.

²These residents are overrepresented in the sample.

³The Maverick Square area was oversampled to increase the representation of Latinos and foreign born residents.

Margin of error = ±5%

APPENDIX B: PREFERENCES FOR SERVICES, RESOURCES, AND AMENITIES**Table 1B: Perceptions about services, resources, and amenities**

	<u>Want More</u>		<u>Happy with it</u>		<u>Want Less</u>		<u>Don't know</u>	
	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%
Gambling Facilities	96	26%	53	14%	194	52%	31	8%
Handicapped Parking	112	30%	143	38%	65	17%	59	16%
Diversity	140	37%	189	50%	32	9%	15	4%
Nightlife venues	171	45%	109	29%	82	22%	17	4%
Day Care	181	48%	116	31%	12	3%	69	18%
Dog Parks	205	55%	103	27%	30	8%	37	10%
Public Transportation	224	58%	152	40%	2	1%	5	1%
English Language Classes	237	62%	83	22%	10	3%	55	14%
Parking	252	66%	108	28%	9	2%	14	4%
Active Recreation	258	67%	102	26%	6	2%	20	5%
Discuss Local Issues	262	70%	97	26%	2	1%	15	4%
Live Performance Venues	266	70%	90	24%	19	5%	6	2%
Parks	293	77%	76	20%	6	2%	7	2%
Family Entertainment	320	82%	50	13%	13	3%	5	1%
Affordable Fresh Food	328	84%	54	14%	4	1%	3	1%

NOTE: Chi square tests show that almost all of the differences seen here are statistically significant. The exception to this is with handicapped parking. There is no statistically significant difference between wanting more and being happy with handicapped parking.

Margin of error = $\pm 5\%$

APPENDIX C: PREFERENCES FOR COMMERCIAL DEVELOPMENT

Table 1C: Preferences for development

	<u>Want More</u>		<u>Happy with it</u>		<u>Want Less</u>		<u>Don't know</u>	
	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%
Retail Development	262	69%	98	26%	14	4%	8	2%
Office Development	190	51%	135	36%	27	7%	23	6%
Industrial Development ¹	124	33%	119	32%	114	30%	18	5%

¹There is no statistically significant differences between those who want more, less or are happy with the amount or type of industrial development.
Margin of error = ±5%

APPENDIX D: PREFERENCES FOR HOUSING DEVELOPMENT

Table 1D: Preferences for housing

	<u>Want More</u>		<u>Happy with it</u>		<u>Want Less</u>		<u>Don't know</u>	
	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%
Affordable Housing	203	53%	74	19%	98	25%	10	3%
Market Rate Housing	232	62%	88	23%	35	9%	22	6%

NOTE: Chi square tests show that the differences seen here are statistically significant.
 Margin of error = ±5%